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The value of enhanced geothermal systems for the energy transition in California[†]

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Enhanced Geothermal Systems (EGS) offer a promising solution to decarbonizing electricity grids by providing clean firm power. Using the BRIDGES gas-electric capacity expansion model, this study explored the techno-economic impacts of integrating EGS into California's electricity and gas sectors. We evaluated multiple EGS-focused scenarios by varying drilling depth, seismic exclusion zones, and dispatch flexibility. This allowed us to determine the influence of these factors on system capacity, costs, and emission reductions. Results showed that allowing drilling depths up to 7 km yielded up to 82 GW of EGS capacity by 2045, reducing total system capacity requirement by 40% and system costs by 8.6% compared to cases without EGS. Flexible EGS dispatch further decreased system costs by 12.3%, although it accelerated reservoir depletion in the long term. EGS also reduced reliance on power-to-gas systems and supported electrification of heating, decreasing the total power-to-gas capacity by 50% compared to cases without EGS. This study demonstrated that EGS could be a critical component in achieving California's 2045 net-zero emissions target, offering significant cost reductions and enhanced system reliability across both the electricity and gas sectors.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The global pursuit of sustainable and environmentally friendly energy sources has intensified in response to the growing concerns over climate change^{1,2}. However, the accelerated transition from traditional fossil fuels to renewable and low-carbon energy sources has prompted new challenges for electricity grids. Renewables with variable generation can cause a mismatch between power demand and supply. The increased additions of intermittent renewables has led to frequent oversupply, where the anticipated generation exceeds the concurrent demand, and wasteful energy curtailment³. Without substantial investments in energy storage and demand response, achieving decarbonization goals would be challenging⁴. Also, 24/7 clean power resources will be crucial to meet rapid growth in data center power demand, which is forecasted to make up 8% of the total United States power demand by 2030⁵.

In California, the progress towards net-zero carbon economy has been highly dependent on the rapid growth of solar and wind electricity, as well as electrification of transportation and heating. However, the increasing reliance on weather-dependent renew-

ables can raise grid reliability challenges, which mandates careful resource planning. California solar and wind gross power generation during the summer is 40-60% higher than winter, with frequent extended periods of limited solar generation occurring in winter months⁶. The high penetration of solar power in the California grid has resulted in oversupply during the middle of the day. This formed the infamous "duck curve", where the day's net load (gross electric load minus solar and wind generation) drops around noon and rapidly increases toward the evening hours⁷. It also led to frequent and significant solar and wind power curtailments. For instance, The California Independent System Operator (CAISO) reported that 2.4 TWh of utility-scale solar and wind were curtailed in 2022, 63% greater than total curtailments in 2021⁸. With the high penetration of solar resources, it is common to have excess generation during mid-day hours, yielding negative pricing and generation curtailment. Additionally, the intermittency of solar and wind often resulted in abrupt shortages in power generation, causing spikes in electricity prices.

Solar resources are characterized with a diminishing effective load carrying capability. Additional investments in solar alone would only shift the peak to later hours during the day. In other words, intermittent resources alone cannot drive a reliable net-zero portfolio. Batteries are being installed rapidly in California and are technically effective at providing capacity for a few hours diurnally. However, batteries are not economic for longer periods because they also suffer from a diminishing effective load carry-

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ing capability, where additional investments in batteries would flatten the peak further, requiring storage for longer hours and reducing the arbitrage value of the shifted power. If further intermittent renewable capacities were installed to meet grid reliability standards, there would be an enormous excess of rarely used generation and batteries. Currently, fossil resources are often dispatched during peak hours to maintain grid reliability. Whereas fossil fuel resources have dominated the supply of dispatchable capacity, this trend will change to meet climate commitments. This raises the need for "clean firm power": carbon-free power resources that are always available for as long as needed. Diversity of resources across dispatch capabilities is also desirable and found to further reduce the costs of full grid decarbonization⁹. Generally, a renewable resource is more appealing when it can cost-effectively integrate in the energy mix, and also shift its power output to span diverse forms of dispatch, e.g., baseload, hourly, daily, and seasonal.

Among the diverse array of renewables, geothermal power is a key contender in the transition towards a greener and more resilient energy landscape. Geothermal energy harnesses the Earth's natural heat to generate electricity, offering a reliable and steady power supply^{10,11}. However, conventional geothermal systems (i.e., hydrothermal) are relatively rare and geographically limited as they require the natural co-occurrence of high temperature, in-situ fluid for heat transport, and permeable/fractured rock for fluid flow. Although the United States is the leading country in conventional geothermal power generation, it only represents 0.4% of the nationwide electricity generation¹².

Recent technological advancements and successful field implementations have demonstrated commercial prospects for enhanced geothermal systems (EGS). In EGS, heat transport and fluid flow are supplemented artificially by water injection and rock stimulation, respectively¹³. EGS are applicable across geographies, as naturally elevated subsurface temperatures are always present across depths¹⁴. As a zero-carbon and small-footprint technology¹⁵, EGS represent a promising option for cost-effectively decarbonizing electricity grids. Hence, conducting a comprehensive techno-economic analysis is useful and important to estimate the supply potential, economic viability, and geographical favorability of EGS.

1.2 Literature review

Several studies estimated that EGS technology has an absolute potential power generation capacity across the continental United States of 4,000–15,000 GW^{16–20}. These estimates were governed by multiple factors: accuracy of subsurface temperature predictions, reservoir temperature decline rate over time, heat-to-power conversion efficiency, and granularity of EGS project life cycle simulations. Importantly, these studies were based on two independent subsurface temperature models developed for shallow (0–3 km) and deep (3–10 km) subsurface by researchers at the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)²¹ and Southern Methodist University (SMU)²², respectively. However, the SMU and NREL models have several shortcomings, e.g., low spatial

resolution, dismissal of areas with convective upflow, amongst others²³. Specifically, comparing the 3 km and 3.5 km layers of the NREL and SMU models shows that predicted values of temperature-at-depth decreases on average by nearly 40°C over a short interval of 0.5 km; hence, the estimated temperatures are inconsistent with the understanding that temperature generally increases with depth. Second, these studies assumed a fixed annual reservoir decline rate. For instance, Augustine *et al.*¹⁶ assumed a fixed thermal decline rate of 0.3%. Third, in estimating the heat-to-power conversion efficiency, they assumed that efficiency was a discrete function of the reservoir temperature only (i.e., one efficiency value for each reservoir temperature range of 25°C), with no regard to the spatiotemporal variations in ambient temperature. Fourth, the aforementioned studies on EGS supply characterization performed techno-economic modeling using the Geothermal Electricity Technology Evaluation Model (GETEM)²⁴, which is limited to annual timesteps, fixed linear annual reservoir temperature decline, fixed ambient temperatures, and baseload operations.

To mitigate the inconsistency of combining the NREL and SMU subsurface temperature maps, Aljubran and Horne²³ developed a new three-dimensional thermal Earth model for the continental United States using interpolative physics-informed graph neural networks. To train this model, they collected and curated over 400,000 measured bottomhole temperature data points alongside other physical quantities, such as rock thermal conductivity, surface heat flow, average surface temperature, elevation, sediment thickness, magnetic anomaly, gravity anomaly, Uranium radiation, Thorium radiation, Potassium radiation, seismicity, electric conductivity, and proximity to faults and volcanoes. They estimated the annual net generation potential to be nearly 309 times greater than the 2023 United States power consumption of 4,014 TWh. They also estimated a total gross EGS capacity potential of 245,032 GW nationwide, an order of magnitude greater than earlier studies, which was attributed to several reasons²⁵. Previous studies relied on the SMU maps which predicted temperatures to be, on average, 29.3% lower across depths compared to the model by Aljubran and Horne²³. Also, they assumed that the EGS power potential per rock volume was in the range of 0.59–1.19 MW/km³ for resource temperatures of 150–350°C. This was an order of magnitude lower than practical observations which indicated that a 210°C reservoir, for instance, has a power density of nearly 10 MW/km³^{26,27}. The techno-economic model by Aljubran and Horne²⁵ rather indicated a nationwide average of 11 MW/km² across depths, which was more aligned with practical observations. Although the estimated EGS power potential was large, the amount that could be economically integrated into the grid is likely much smaller than this total potential.

1.3 Study objective

In this study, we investigated the value of incorporating EGS into the California energy system. We achieved this through capacity expansion modeling with the objective of cost-effectively decarbonizing the California power and gas networks. Based on the most recently developed EGS resource potential estimates²⁸,

we explored different EGS supply scenarios: baseload/flexible generation dispatch, baseline/advanced drilling costs, allowable maximum drilling depth, and land exclusion based on seismically active regions. We adopted BRIDGES (Building Resilient Integrated Decarbonized Gas-Electric Systems)²⁹, a gas-electricity sector coupled capacity expansion model developed for energy systems planning, to determine the optimal energy transition pathway for California in the presence of EGS resources.

2 Methodology

The methodology consists of integrating outputs from a techno-economic assessment of EGS, which are fed into a capacity expansion model. This process is summarized in Fig. 1.

2.1 Enhanced geothermal systems

2.1.1 Resource Potential

Based on the United States thermal Earth model and subsequent EGS resource supply developed by Aljubran and Horne^{23,25}, we constructed EGS resource potential across different scenarios for California. Whereas earlier studies estimated EGS supply potential in California of 40–700 GW^{16,18,19}, our model predicted nearly 20,882 GW in total. Fig. 2 compares the adopted EGS supply curves for California to other models. Each of these studies included baseline and advanced scenarios involving various assumptions of EGS parameters, mainly drilling costs. The adopted EGS supply curves were modeled using the Flexible Geothermal Economics Model (FGEM)³⁰, which used hourly timesteps to capture the effect of ambient temperature. They involved an analytical model to simulate the produced temperature decline over the lifetime of EGS fractured reservoirs under various operational strategies. This model represents a one-dimensional single-continuum semi-infinite transient diffusion-convection problem and allows for variable well flow rates and injection temperatures³¹. Additionally, these EGS supply curves were developed based on ambient temperature forecasts with a nominal spatial resolution of 4 km² at an hourly frequency, generated based on open-source generative machine learning methods recently developed by researchers at NREL for meteorological modeling³². The FGEM financial models were used to estimate project capital expenditure (CAPEX), operational expenditure (OPEX), and levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) with a discount rate of 7%. Spatially variant transmission line costs³¹ were also considered based on 2 USD/mile-kW, and 2022 baseline drilling costs as originally developed for the Geothermal Electricity Technology Evaluation Model²⁴ based on actual geothermal drilling projects³³. The scenario of advanced drilling was based on actual 2024 drilling costs reported for EGS projects in Nevada and Utah, which indicated a reduction in drilling costs by nearly 50%³⁴.

2.1.2 Sensitivity to allowable drilling depths

In conventional geothermal development, wells are typically drilled to depths shallower than 4 km to access hydrothermal resources and produce naturally occurring hot water and steam^{35,36}. Meanwhile, EGS only requires elevated geothermal gradients, so it offers the potential to tap into deeper geother-

mal resources, extending the reach to depths greater than 4 km. However, drilling deeper may involve challenges, such as harder geological formations, highly fractured zones, and higher pressures and temperatures that require advanced drilling equipment and materials. The economic risks are also substantial, as the costs of drilling and completing wells increase parabolically with depth. Nevertheless, a number of wells have been drilled to depths of 7 km and deeper in the United States and around the world. Tapping into deeper resources is favorable, as the power plant thermal efficiency is greater for higher geofluid temperatures, which resulted in favorable project CAPEX. Depending on the risk-reward portfolio of geothermal investors, there could be more or less interest in drilling to deeper depths. Thus, we investigated the least-cost optimal grid system design for scenarios where EGS development is limited to maximum depths of 4 km, 5 km, 6 km, and 7 km.

2.1.3 Sensitivity to seismicity

Considering possible seismicity effects is crucial when considering the deployment of EGS, which could induce seismic events by the alteration of stress conditions in the subsurface. Considering these events is essential to ensure the safe and sustainable development of EGS. Whereas it is beyond our scope to perform detailed geological and geophysical investigation to identify fault lines, stress fields, and the mechanical properties of the rock formations nationwide, we focused on analyzing the potential effect of seismic events on limiting EGS deployment. Researchers at the USGS modeled natural seismicity nationwide, and estimated the chance of any level of damaging earthquake shaking in 100 years³⁷. Natural seismic events are more frequent and damaging in faulted zones, and are indicative of increased risks of damaging induced seismicity during hydraulic stimulation and injection operations that are associated with EGS projects. We created EGS resource potential scenarios by excluding lands with relatively high risk of natural seismicity. In particular, we considered three thresholds on the chance of any level of damaging earthquake shaking in 100 years, namely 95% (Low), 85% (Moderate), and 75% (High). Fig 3 shows the extent of land exclusions nationwide based on these thresholds. We note that significant California land was excluded as a result, especially along the Pacific Coast.

2.1.4 Sensitivity to power dispatch

Additionally, we evaluated the potential EGS deployment when these resources were operated flexibly, where power output was varied to maximize generation over the project lifetime. Independent of system costs, it was found that geothermal developers could reduce LCOE by 6.4% if they opted for flexible dispatch compared to the business-as-usual baseload dispatch with constant production mass flow rates²⁵. The considered flexible dispatch approach involved minimal design changes to EGS projects, relying on wellhead throttling and power plant bypass. In particular, the production mass flow rate was allowed to increase by a maximum of 30% to maintain power generation as high as possible throughout the project lifetime. We considered flexible generation scenarios in our capacity expansion modeling

Fig. 1 Schematic highlighting the work flow for the inputs and data processing using FGEM³⁰ and their connection to the BRIDGES capacity expansion model²⁹.

Fig. 2 Comparison of different EGS supply curves for California across baseline and advanced scenarios for EGS techno-economics¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

efforts, as they were associated with limited drops in EGS capacity factor during warmer seasons compared to reductions ob-

served under baseload operations. Thus, we used BRIDGES to optimize the energy system capacity under the EGS scenarios of

Fig. 3 Land exclusion scenarios based on the chance of any level of damaging earthquake shaking in 100 years, using a range of probability thresholds. Gray pixels represent excluded land due to seismicity. The color of non-excluded points within California designates the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) for an EGS built and operating in that particular point.

baseline/advanced drilling rates and baseload/flexible power dispatch.

2.1.5 Supply scenarios

We explored different scenarios for capacity expansion modeling in California based on different EGS resource potential settings, as seen in Table 1. These settings were based on different factors, namely baseload/flexible dispatch, baseline/advanced drilling costs, allowable maximum drilling depth, and land exclusion based on seismically active regions. Figs. A.1 and A.2 show the EGS resource supply and average capacity factors across these scenarios. Note that capacity factors were modeled at hourly resolution with power plant thermal efficiencies and EGS reservoir depletion over years simulated using FGEM with ambient temperature forecasts generated based on the NREL generative machine learning model³². The resultant installed capacity of various energy resources and system costs were compared across scenarios and with a baseline setting that did not allow EGS development (scenario “No-EGS”).

Data are presented for 16 California climate zones, as modeled in the BRIDGES model, showing a large spread between climate zones. Considering scenario 1-D with baseline drilling, 7 km maximum allowable depth, baseload dispatch, and no land exclusions of seismically active zones, Fig. 4 shows EGS resource supply across the 16 climate zones in California. Higher temperature resources naturally provided the most lucrative EGS targets, i.e., low CAPEX, high capacity potential. We observed significant capacity potential across climate zones in the range of 4,000–8,000 USD/kW CAPEX, which was competitive and comparable to other clean firm technologies in California³⁸. EGS generation was modeled for each climate zone using grades corresponding to capacity available at different costs. This was important to capture the different qualities/grades of EGS in each climate zone.

Seven CAPEX-based EGS grades were constructed with percentile thresholds of 1%, 5%, 10%, 25%, 50%, and 75%. The median resource characteristics (available capacity and costs) (capital and operating). Similarly, each climate zone consists of variable capacity factors.

Table 1 EGS scenarios for capacity expansion modeling in California

Scenario	Drilling Performance	Maximum Drilling Depth	Power Dispatch Type	Seismic Exclusions
No-EGS	NA	NA	NA	None
1-A	Baseline	4 km	Baseload	None
1-B	Baseline	5 km	Baseload	None
1-C	Baseline	6 km	Baseload	None
1-D	Baseline	7 km	Baseload	None
2-B	Baseline	7 km	Baseload	Low
2-C	Baseline	7 km	Baseload	Moderate
2-D	Baseline	7 km	Baseload	High
3-B	Baseline	4 km	Baseload	High
3-C	Baseline	5 km	Baseload	High
3-D	Baseline	6 km	Baseload	High
4-A	Baseline	7 km	Flexible	None
4-B	Advanced	7 km	Baseload	None
4-C	Advanced	7 km	Flexible	None

Fig. 4 EGS resource supply potential across the 16 California climate zones for scenario 1-D with baseline drilling, 7 km maximum allowable depth, baseload dispatch, and no land exclusions of seismically active zones. Each panel shows a set of lines corresponding to different target depths.

2.2 Capacity expansion modeling

The analysis was conducted using BRIDGES, which is a capacity expansion model utilized for energy systems planning, developed by Von Wald *et al.*²⁹. BRIDGES is a linear optimization (cost minimization) model that captures the combined gas-electric energy systems interactions. BRIDGES is modeled in the JuMP mathematical programming framework, based on the Julia programming language³⁹. BRIDGES utilizes the Gurobi optimization solver⁴⁰. The optimization runs were conducted using Sherlock - Stanford's High Performance Computing Cluster⁴¹, with solve times of \approx one hour using 16 core AMD EPYC 7543 processors up to 100 GB of RAM (time and RAM usage depend on particular scenarios run).

The geographic scope of interest was California. Further details of the baseline models of the California energy transition using BRIDGES are described in⁴²⁻⁴⁴. California was modeled as 16 connected zones, whose regions were based on the 16 climate zones defined by the California Energy Commission⁴²⁻⁴⁴. Two Offshore and four export nodes were also included to model interactions with neighboring states/regions, for a total of 22 modeled nodes. These nodes were not fully connected in either the electricity or gas trade networks, with the internode connectivity taken from real infrastructure maps of California⁴²⁻⁴⁴.

From a temporal perspective, the presence of energy storage systems necessitates the modeling of temporal chronology⁴⁵. This necessity arises because the state of charge of a given storage system on a given day is dependent on the states of previous days. However, modeling a full year using an hourly time series approach would lead to computation intractability. Thus, representative days with storage-linking constraints were used to represent each investment year⁴⁵, such that the storage dynamics were preserved. In particular, each investment year was modeled using ten representative days, including all 24 hours per day. With a five-year interval, five investment time horizons were considered in this work, namely 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040 and 2045.

The design variables were the investment (building and retirement of system capacities) decisions and operational dispatch of existing and newly installed capacity of energy systems, including generators, storage systems, power-to-gas facilities, and end-use appliances. Besides mass balance and flow constraints of power and gas, and operational constraints for the systems (ex: a battery cannot discharge more energy than its rated capacity), a decarbonization policy constraint was set to achieve net-zero emissions across all sectors in California by 2045. This policy constraint resulted in the retirement of fossil fuel-based systems and installation of new renewable energy technologies.

2.2.1 Renewable Energy Resources in California

Capacity expansion of renewable energy resources in California were constrained based on land-use availability and build rates. Available wind and solar capacities were based on the "Reference Access" Supply Curve by NREL^{46,47}, which provides supply curve data that applies land area exclusions based on physical constraints (e.g., wetlands, building footprints) and protected lands. The supply curve data are grid-based region-specific information on available capacity and wind speed and solar irradiance

for wind and solar, respectively. The total build capacity for each climate zone was constrained to half the available capacity, less any built capacity, to achieve more realistic projected builds of solar and wind systems.

2.2.2 Gas-Electric Sector Coupling

In addition to decarbonizing electricity generation, the BRIDGES model addresses the decarbonization of California's heat demand. The model covers the natural gas network and infrastructure. This gas infrastructure interacts with the electricity network in two ways: (1) the gas system supplies natural gas to gas-fired power plants, and (2) the model can utilize the electricity in a given climate zone to produce synthetic natural gas using power-to-gas processes (including both electrolytic H₂ and synthetic methane). As a result, the model more realistically represents the energy infrastructure by combining both the gas and electricity networks, particularly their interactions in the simultaneous decarbonization of electricity and heat demand.

Two types of heat demand sources were modeled in this work: end-use appliances in the residential and commercial sectors, and industrial heat. With end-use appliances, BRIDGES tracks the existing stock of gas and electric fueled appliance and allows for endogenous stock turnover and fuel-switching of these appliances upon failure. This approach couples the gas and electric sector via demand-side decarbonization levers. Industrial gas demand covers heat demands - typically served by burning fossil fuels - that peaks at 22 GW of heat demanded in California. It was assumed that at most 70% of the industrial heat demand could be electrified using an electric boiler, since around 70% of industrial heat demand requires temperatures below 500°C, which is easily satisfied by the electric boiler⁴⁸. The remaining 30% of hard-to-decarbonize high temperature heat is assumed to be met with gas (either fossil-fuel or through power-to-gas). This assumption will be explored in future work focusing on industrial decarbonization in the BRIDGES model.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Sensitivity to allowable drilling depths

In addition to EGS, BRIDGES involved various energy generation resources, such as solar, solar thermal, onshore/offshore wind, nuclear, hydropower, conventional geothermal, biopower, open/combined-cycle gas, natural gas with carbon capture and sequestration (CCS), and coal. Various storage options were also included, namely Li-ion battery, pumped hydro, hydrogen, and iron-air units. Fig. 5 shows the total installed resource capacity in California across years for a baseline scenario with no EGS compared to different scenarios of maximum allowable EGS target depths. In the absence of EGS, the total installed system power capacity was 272 GW by 2045, dominated by solar, wind, and natural gas with CCS, and also involving hydropower, conventional geothermal, Li-ion, and pumped hydro. We note that the system was fully decarbonized by 2045. Also, the installed power capacity increased more rapidly between 2040-2045, which was incentivized by the technology growth and associated learning curves over time.

Considering maximum allowable drilling depth scenarios in-

Fig. 5 Comparison of total installed resource capacity in California across years for different maximum allowable EGS target depths.

volving EGS resource supply, the total installed system power supply capacity by 2045 was in the range of 160–180 GW. This was significantly smaller than the no-EGS scenario because EGS is typically associated with higher capacity factors compared to intermittent resources. This was observed as a significant drop in the total solar PV and battery storage capacities required to be in-

stalled. The EGS capacity installed by 2045 across the maximum allowable depth scenarios was 70–82 GW. Generally, allowing for deeper drilling resulted in increased EGS deployment. Deeper geothermal wells unlock higher subsurface temperatures, leading to improved thermodynamic efficiency for power generation. Moreover, increased production temperature result in an increas-

ingly nonlinear growth in the power plant efficiency Aljubran and Horne²⁵. This enhancement in conversion efficiency directly influenced LCOE, making deeper wells more economically competitive despite the increased capital costs associated with drilling to deeper resources. Consequently, deeper and more favorable resources were associated with greater capacity factors, hence smaller EGS installed capacity was required to meet the system electricity and gas demand in the 7 km scenario compared to the 6 km counterpart. Additionally, deeper resources are generally associated with enhanced longevity due to the favorable conductive heat recharge rates. Shallower wells tend to experience faster thermal depletion due to limited recharge rates from the surrounding rock⁴⁹. The longer operational lifetime and slower depletion rates of deeper geothermal resources could improve the long-term economic viability.

Compared to the no-EGS scenario, the total system cost to meet California's 2045 decarbonization goals was reduced by nearly 8.6% for the scenario of 7 km drilling depth. Recalling that demand in BRIDGES was modeled endogenously and observing Fig. A.4, we note that power-to-gas conversion was significantly smaller after introducing EGS. This is reasonable because power-to-gas conversion was associated with low efficiency of nearly 50%, hence it was more optimal to electrify appliances further in the presence of a relatively economic clean firm resource with high capacity factors like EGS. Fig. 6 shows the spatial distribution of the installed EGS capacity by 2045 for different maximum allowable EGS target depths. We note that the most significant EGS installations were in climate zones 1 and 2, alongside the northern California segment of the Pacific Coast. Additionally, the 4 km scenario showed a greater spatial spread of EGS development due to limited supply per climate zone compared to scenarios where EGS development at deeper depths was allowed.

3.2 Sensitivity to seismicity

As seen in Fig. 7, under the High seismic land exclusion scenario, greater total system capacity was required due to the smaller EGS capacity installed and greater solar PV and storage capacity installed. Whereas offshore wind and natural gas with CCS were generally suboptimal in the presence of EGS, that was not the case under Moderate and High seismic land exclusion scenarios of EGS. Fig. 8 shows the spatial distribution of the installed EGS capacity by 2045 for different seismic land exclusion scenario. We note that multiple climate zones along the Pacific Coast were completely unavailable for EGS development under the Moderate and High seismic scenarios. Instead, BRIDGES converged to a solution with less EGS installation in these cases with significant EGS development along the Sierra Nevada and the western flank of the Great Basin. Furthermore, we evaluated a more conservative set of scenarios combining the High seismic land exclusion criterion with shallower maximum allowable depths. Under an overly conservative scenario with High seismic land exclusions and 4 km maximum allowable drilling depth, a total of 47 GW of EGS capacity was deployed, 40% smaller than the 81 GW installed capacity under the scenario of 7 km allowable drilling depth and no seismic land exclusions.

While the exclusion of seismically active zones can reduce the potential for induced seismic events, it also presents trade-offs in terms of resource availability and overall system costs. By integrating seismic hazard models into the early planning stages of EGS projects, operators can identify the most geologically stable areas while maximizing geothermal potential. This could be done in future implementations of EGS in capacity expansion modeling by including more detailed treatment of drilling safety and induced seismicity in the constraint set of the model. Also, risk mitigation strategies in EGS reservoir stimulation and production with respect to site-specific geomechanical conditions (e.g., controlling injection pressures and fluid volumes, onsite seismic monitoring using observation wells and fiber optics), can reduce the likelihood of seismicity while ensuring resource productivity.

3.3 Sensitivity to drilling rates and dispatch

The sensitivity to drilling rates and dispatch strategies highlights the intricate balance between technological advancements, operational flexibility, and system-wide decarbonization goals. The variation in drilling rates and the adoption of flexible dispatch models play a crucial role in determining the extent to which Enhanced Geothermal Systems (EGS) can reduce reliance on intermittent resources and storage systems. Fig. 9 compares the total installed resource capacity in California across years for baseline/advanced drilling rates and baseload/flexible dispatch strategies.

We first note that flexible dispatch results in lower system capacity requirements in the early years because flexible EGS operations were associated with greater capacity factors. However, due to the more rapid EGS reservoir depletion under flexible dispatch, the system installed capacity under flexible EGS operations became greater by 2045 compared to baseload EGS dispatch. Overall, the flexible/advanced scenario resulted in a total of 97 GW EGS deployment and 12.3% lower total system cost compared to the no-EGS scenario.

Note that the flexible dispatch approach in consideration involved was based on wellhead throttling and power plant bypass. It was only aimed at maximizing power generation, especially during warmer hours (i.e., daytime and summer hours), rather than shifting generation potential. Hence, it had no fundamental change to the role that geothermal energy plays in the grid as a clean firm resource. Nevertheless, this form of flexibility was favorable and reduced the need for large-scale battery storage and the reliance on natural gas peaker plants, which are traditionally used to balance the grid during periods of high variability.

While flexible dispatch was advantageous in terms of overall system cost and reliance on storage, it introduced trade-offs in terms of reservoir longevity and overall system capacity. As observed in flexible dispatch scenarios, the higher initial capacity factors resulted in more rapid reservoir decline, necessitating additional system capacity in later years. This dynamic creates a tradeoff between optimizing short-term energy output and preserving long-term reservoir sustainability. Different operational strategies can help mitigate the effects of faster depletion by allowing for periods of reduced output to enable thermal recovery

Fig. 6 Spatial distribution of the installed EGS capacity by 2045 for different maximum allowable EGS target depths.

in the reservoir, extending the life of the resource while still providing flexible, dispatchable power. In practice, these decisions will be developer-specific investment decisions based on risk tolerance, available interest rates, and developer preference.

Finally, we compared our estimates to other studies, although their scope was focused on electricity only and involved different EGS supply curves, seen in Fig. 2. In the Enhanced Geothermal Shot Analysis study, Augustine *et al.*¹⁶ performed capacity expansion modeling to forecast the amount of EGS electricity generation that could be deployed in the U.S. by 2050 the ReEDS capacity expansion model. They concluded that, under the advanced IT scenario, California would have 27.9 GW of EGS capacity installed by 2050. In another study, Ricks *et al.*¹⁸ researched the same question using the GenX capacity expansion model and concluded that, under advanced drilling rates and flexible generation, California would have nearly 25-35 GW of EGS capacity installed by 2050. In both studies, the installed EGS capacity represented nearly 20-35% of the total California system power capacity across scenarios. In our study, we found that the installed EGS capacity by 2045 was in the range of nearly 25–60% of total capacity across the analyzed scenarios. We attributed our higher forecasts of installed EGS capacity in California to several factors. Our EGS resource supply curves were more optimistic compared to those used in the previous studies. Also, BRIDGES co-optimized electricity and gas markets simultaneously which unlocked further endogenous demand that prompted power-to-gas conversion, allowing for additional EGS capacities to be installed. Additionally, the BRIDGES model aggregates the power transmission capacity based on the 16 climate zones of California, which could have led to overestimating how the allowable electricity transmission across climate zones allowing for clustering EGS deployment in the most favorable zones.

3.4 Impact of gas-sector decarbonization

Decarbonization of the gas sector is essential for achieving California’s broader climate goals, as the state moves toward net-zero emissions across both electricity and heating sectors. A major pathway for decarbonizing the gas sector is the electrification of heat demand, particularly for residential and industrial heating. In particular, the heating sector, especially in colder climates, requires a stable and continuous supply of energy, which intermittent renewable sources like solar and wind cannot guarantee without extensive storage. In industrial contexts, where high-temperature heat is required, electrification can be challenging, as the efficiency of electric heating systems can diminish at higher temperatures. By decarbonizing the electricity supply, EGS allows these electric heating systems to operate with a much lower carbon footprint compared to traditional gas-fired systems, making industrial decarbonization more achievable.

The BRIDGES model captures the dynamics of decarbonization associated with the electrification of heating demand. This heat electrification is particularly shown in Fig. A.11, wherein more than 80 GW of capacity was required for electric boilers and power-to-methane systems to provide heat with net-zero emissions in the absence of EGS. However, with EGS allowed to be built by the model, the required capacity for clean heating systems was reduced to less than 50 GW due to the availability of clean firm resources in the form of EGS. This reduction in clean heat system capacity was also accompanied by reductions in total system costs. Thus, EGS could enhance the electrification of heating demand, which is otherwise currently met by CO₂-emitting fossil gas.

4 Conclusions

This study investigated the role of EGS in decarbonizing California’s energy grid. We used the BRIDGES capacity expansion framework that couples the electricity and gas sectors in a uni-

Fig. 7 Comparison of total installed resource capacity in California across years for different seismic land exclusion criteria.

fied model, which allowed for a detailed exploration of how EGS could complement intermittent renewable energy sources, reduce storage needs, and provide firm, low-carbon power that supports grid reliability and stability. Our sensitivity analysis showed that the maximum allowable drilling depth for EGS has a substantial impact on system capacity and costs. When deeper drilling (up to 7 km) is allowed, EGS deployment could reach up to 82

GW by 2045, which reduced total installed system capacity by nearly 40% compared to scenarios without EGS. Access to higher-temperature resources at greater depths increased the capacity factor and reduced the need for both solar PV and battery storage, lowering system costs by 8.6%. We also found that excluding high-risk seismic areas led to an increase in total system capacity requirement by 10–15%, as lower EGS deployment must be

Fig. 8 Spatial distribution of ins of the installed EGS capacity by 2045 for different seismic land exclusion scenario.

compensated by additional solar and storage capacity. Additionally, flexible dispatch of EGS proved to be an effective strategy for enhancing the value of geothermal energy in a grid increasingly reliant on variable renewables. Our analysis showed that flexible EGS operations could reduce the need for utility-scale battery storage and gas-fired peaker plants, contributing to a 12.3% reduction in total system costs compared to scenarios with baseload EGS. However, flexible dispatch leads to faster reservoir depletion, which must be carefully managed to maintain long-term resource sustainability. The BRIDGES model showed that the deployed power-to-gas capacity could be reduced by 50% in scenarios with EGS, owing to the firm, continuous power supplied by geothermal resources. Furthermore, by supplying electricity for heating technologies, EGS enabled a significant reduction in natural gas consumption in the residential and industrial sectors. The integration of EGS into California's energy system thus accelerated decarbonization across both power and gas sectors, leading to an overall more efficient and cost-effective energy transition.

Fig. 9 Comparison of total installed resource capacity in California across years for baseline/advanced drilling rates and baseload/flexible dispatch strategies.

Author Contributions

Mohammad Aljubran contributed to conceptualization, methodology, implementation and analysis, and writing the first draft. **Dimitri Saad** contributed to conceptualization, methodology, implementation and analysis, and writing the first draft. **Mo Sodwatana** contributed to methodology, analysis, and writing the final draft. **Adam Brandt** contributed to conceptualization, research supervision, and reviewing and editing. **Roland Horne** contributed to conceptualization, research supervision, and re-

viewing and editing.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data Availability

EGS resource supply data across scenarios are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13959731>.

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Appendix

A Additional Visualizations

Fig. A.1 EGS resource supply across the different scenarios considered for capacity expansion modeling in this work.

Fig. A.2 EGS resource average capacity factors over time for the different scenarios considered for capacity expansion modeling in this work.

Fig. A.3 Comparison of total generation in California across years for different maximum allowable EGS target depths.

Fig. A.4 Comparison of power to gas/heat conversion capacity in California across years for different maximum allowable EGS target depths.

Fig. A.5 Comparison of total generation in California across years for different seismic land exclusion criteria.

Fig. A.6 Comparison of relative total California system cost in 2045 for different seismic land exclusion criteria.

Fig. A.7 Comparison of power to gas/heat conversion capacity in California across years for different seismic land exclusion criteria.

Fig. A.8 Spatial distribution of ins of the installed EGS capacity by 2045 of the High seismic land exclusion criterion for different maximum allowable drilling depths.

Fig. A.9 Comparison of total generation in California across years of the High seismic land exclusion criterion for different maximum allowable drilling depths.

Fig. A.10 Comparison of relative total California system cost in 2045 of the High seismic land exclusion criterion for different maximum allowable drilling depths.

Fig. A.11 Comparison of power to gas/heat conversion capacity in California across years of the High seismic land exclusion criterion for different maximum allowable drilling depths.